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Evaluation of "Effective Ionic Diameter" 'A' from Hydration Number 'h' of a Strong Electrolyte Solution

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Manuscript received 16 November 1981,
accepted 28 September 1982

It has been shown in a previous publication¹ that above 0.1 M, variation with concentration of the mean molal activity coefficient γ of the ions of a strong 1 : 1 electrolyte solution can be represented by the following equation,

$$\log \gamma = -\frac{B}{\sqrt{A}} C^{1/2} + \log \frac{C}{m d_0} + \frac{0.018 m r (r + h - \nu)}{2.3 \nu (1 + 0.018 m r)} + \frac{h - \nu}{\nu} \log (1 + 0.018 m r) - \frac{h}{\nu} \log (1 - 0.018 m h) \quad (1)$$

where B is a constant which can be calculated from theory, A the effective ionic diameter, C the molar and m the molal concentration respectively, d_0 the density of the solvent, r the volume fraction, h the hydration number and ν the number of ions formed by a molecule of the electrolyte.

It may be mentioned that according to Glueckauf² and Robinson and Stokes³, $\log \gamma$ may be expressed as follows :

$$\log \gamma = \log \gamma^{el} + \log \gamma^{vis} \quad \dots (2)$$

In equation (1) $-\frac{B}{\sqrt{A}} C^{1/2} + \log \frac{C}{m d_0}$ represent

$\log \gamma^{el}$ as deduced by the author¹ and the rest represent $\log \gamma^{vis}$ as deduced by Glueckauf².

For each electrolyte the values of the two empirical constants A and h are to be found from experimental data on the activity coefficient of the ions. The two constants will, however, be reduced effectively to one if a quantitative relation can be found between them.

It may be mentioned that A can also be found from data on equivalent conductivity λ of a strong 1 : 1 electrolyte solution using the following equation deduced by the author⁴.

$$\lambda = \lambda_g - \frac{mG}{\sqrt{A}} C^{1/2} \quad \dots (3)$$

where λ_g represents equivalent conductance at infinite dilution and m and G are constants which can be calculated from theory.

In a paper⁵ already published A has been defined by the following expression :

$$A = (r_- + r_+ + H) \quad \dots (4)$$

where r_- and r_+ represent the Pauling radii of the negative and positive ions and H the contribution of hydration of the ions to A, all expressed in Angström unit.

For the chlorides of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Cs^+ and H^+ the following relation has now been found to exist between H and h.

$$\frac{4}{3} \pi H^3 = (h - r) \frac{18}{N} \text{ cc} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{or } H = \left[(h - r) \frac{30}{4.19} \right]^{1/3} \text{ \AA} \quad \dots (5a)$$

In equation (5), 18 is the molar volume of water at 25°, N the Avogadro number and $r = \phi_v / V_w$ where ϕ_v is the apparent molal volume of the electrolyte at concentration 1 N and V_w is the volume of one gram molecule of water ; thus r represents Glueckauf's volume fraction.

In Table 1 are recorded the data on the electrolytes mentioned above. In column 1 of the table under the head miscellaneous are mentioned the electrolyte and the values of the corresponding r. In the columns 6 and 7 of the table are recorded the values of A in Angström found from measurements of activity coefficient¹ and conductance of the ions of the electrolyte⁶ in the concentration ranges 0.001 M to 4.0 M and 0.001 M to 0.1 M, respectively.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF OBSERVED AND CALCULATED VALUES OF A AT 25°

Miscellaneous	$r_- + r_+$	h	Calculated H	Calculated A	Observed A from Acti- vity	Conduc- tance
LiCl r=1.03	2.41	5.60	3.20	5.61	5.62	
NaCl r=1.03	2.76	4.06	2.79	5.55	5.52	5.52
KCl r=1.4	3.14	3.0	2.26	5.40	5.52	5.48
CsCl r=2.3	3.50	2.40	0.89	4.39	4.33	
HCl r=1.05	3.89	5.34	3.11	7.0	6.92	5.59

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that the calculated values of A agree well with those found from measurements of mean molal activity coefficient of the ions. They also agree well with the values of A found from conductivity measurement except in the case of HCl. It may be attributed in the latter case to the peculiar mechanism of conduction of current by the H^+ ion which is assumed to gain by the diameter of the oxygen atom (1.48 Å) in the process. If 1.48 is added to 5.59, we get 7.07 Å which is very close to the calculated value of A of HCl.

It may be pointed out that equation (5) may also be written as follows :

$$N\left(\frac{4}{3}\pi H^3\right) = hV_w - \phi_v \quad \dots (6)$$

The symbols N, H, h, V_w and ϕ_v in equation (6) have the same significance as stated already.

It follows from equation (6) that the binding of water molecules by the ions is accompanied by contraction in volume of the former. Equation (6) may be put in a generalised form by writing it as follows :

$$N\left(\frac{4}{3}\pi H^3\right) = hV_w - \beta\phi_v \quad \dots (6a)$$

where β is a numerical factor which is to be found from experimental data.

For the chlorides of the cations mentioned in Table 1 it appears that at concentration 1 N and 25° the values of β is unity. Since β in equation (6a) is to be found from experimental data, equation (6a) and the others [(6) and (5)] which follow from it should be treated as semi-empirical.

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Interaction of Thallium(I) with Some Plant Auxins at Dropping Mercury Electrode

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Manuscript received 24 March 1981, revised 26 July 1982,
accepted 28 September 1982

3-INDOLEACETIC acid, 3-indolebutyric acid and 1-naphthaleneacetic acid are endogenous plant auxins which play multifarious role in the physiology of plants^{1,2}. No work has so far been reported on the polarographic determination of the stability constants of metal complexes with these plant auxins. In the present investigation, a study of the interaction of thallium(I) with these auxins at dropping mercury electrode in aqueous and aqueous-ethanol mixture media has, therefore, been undertaken.

Experimental

Reagents: Thallium(I) sulphate (B.D.H., AnalaR), 3-indoleacetic acid (E. Merck), 3-indolebutyric acid

(Loba Chemie), and 1-naphthaleneacetic acid (Sisco) were used as such. All other chemicals used were of guaranteed purity. Triple distilled mercury and double distilled water were used. Ethanol was dried successively over lime and anhydrous copper sulphate, and distilled over sodium. The distillate was treated with pure magnesium turnings and a little iodine, warmed under reflux to start the reaction and then allowed to stand till the reaction subsided. The contents were finally distilled at 78° at a take-off ratio of 1 : 5.

Solutions: Stock solution of thallium (0.02 M) was prepared in water and standardized³. The sodium salts of the ligands were prepared and pH of the solutions adjusted with sodium hydroxide using ELICO pH meter model LI-10. Solutions containing the metal ion (4×10^{-4} M) and varying concentrations of the ligand in water, 10% and/or 50% ethanol were prepared at ionic strength 0.5 M maintained with sodium perchlorate.

Solutions of 3-indoleacetic acid, 3-indolebutyric acid and 1-naphthaleneacetic acid (0.004 M) in water, 10% and/or 50% ethanol at ionic strength 0.5 M, adjusted with sodium perchlorate, were titrated with carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 M) at 15 ± 0.1 and/or 25 ± 0.1 °. After accounting for the dilution effect, the values of dissociation constant were calculated according to the method described by Albert and Serjeant⁴ (Table 1).

TABLE 1—pK VALUES OF VARIOUS PLANT AUXINS IN DIFFERENT MEDIA

Auxin	pK (± 0.03)	Temp. °C	Medium % Ethanol
3-Indoleacetic acid	3.75	25	0.00
	4.12	25	10
3-Indolebutyric acid	4.22	25	10
	3.52	25	10
1-Naphthaleneacetic acid	5.10	25	50
	3.61	15	10

The capillary characteristics measured in 0.1 M sodium perchlorate (open circuit) and at a mercury height (h) of 60 cm were $m = 2.113 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$ and $t = 4.04 \text{ sec}$. Purified nitrogen, presaturated with the background solution to be polarographed, was used for deaeration. Electrolysis was carried out in a H-cell in conjunction with an agar-agar plug saturated with sodium chloride. An inert atmosphere was maintained over the solution during electrolysis. Polarograms of 4×10^{-4} M thallium(I) solution were obtained in the presence of different concentrations of the ligand at pH 6.7 ± 0.1 and temperature at 15 ± 0.1 and/or 25 ± 0.1 ° using Radelkis polarograph type OH 102. An IR compensator was used while working with ethanolic solutions. The currents were corrected for the residual current. The resulting polarographic data as a function of ligand concentration which was calculated from the pH of the solution and the pK value of the auxin, are given in Table 2.

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